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Agreements of Love and Friendship in the Merchant of Venice¹

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the connection between the two forms of relationship: contractual and non-contractual. Merchant of Venice highlights the effects of contract for the safeguard of the city of Venice and at the same time focuses the harsh effects alliance and agreement of love and friendship. This is evident in the decisions, actions, and relationships of Antonio, Bassanio, Portia, and Jessica. Although Shakespeare concludes the play on a happy note, in the conclusion one can reach is that, despite its advantages, regimes based on commerce and contract fail to create the conditions for friendship and love to flourish.

INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses the connection between the two forms of relationship: contractual and non-contractual. Merchant of Venice highlights the effects of contract for the safeguard of the city of Venice

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and at the same time focuses the harsh effects alliance and agreement of love and friendship. In the Merchant of Venice, Shakespeare addresses the several compliments of fairness and grace to explorations of the right partnership between Christians and Jews. The majority of scholars have given particular attention to Shylock's character and the concerns associated with him. By looking at both of these features, I explain how a trade and contract environment appears to minimise any reference to self-interest, usefulness and benefit motives. (Venice, Portia and Belmont, 1925) It was stated from the play that, even though a pound of flesh was needed otherwise, Venice would lose its integrity and all commerce and justice will cease to exist, it is an economically dependent city with a rule of contract applied. As Antonio states with Shylock's bond of blood, who requested it. (Lever, 1952)

*The Duke cannot deny the course of laws;
For the commodity that strangers have
With us in Venice, if it is denied,
Will much impeach the justice of the state?
Since the trade and profit of the city*

Consisteth of all nations (III.iii.26–31). (Auden, 1963) Though the implementation of the contract is irrational in this specific situation, the critical advantage for a city like Venice, built and ruled by exchange and contracts is that self-interest interests, usefulness and profit outweigh the inherent propensity towards avoiding, persecuting and killing visitors (Coghill). Christians aim to prosper from or from them, rather than to remove or to murder Jews, and vice versa. In Venice, there is always discrimination, but oppression and assassination do not occur.

As a moral philosophy, the Christian commandment to love your neighbour does not seem to have structured the city: exchange, contracts and benefit paved the route to peace, harmony and tolerance. However, fair and enforceable justice is needed to sustain this harmony. As if this is contradictory to his actions, Antonio would be prosecuted in Venice for the preservation of the rule of law (IV. i.–33. (Hall, 1970) Shylock rightly questions that, if an exemption existed in this situation, the Duke did not violate such arrangements, such as the slave's transaction (i.e., IV.i.89–103; 38–39)? The solution is relatively evident: if contracts were not followed, that would lead to confusion and nobody could be sure. Therefore, the Duke must extend the contract of a pound of flesh in order to preserve peace in the city and the integrity of his power. As we realise later in the game, the deal has been enacted only as "a drops of Christian blood, your lands and your property, whether you spill it are seized by the laws of Venice." (IV.i.309–11)(Waddington, 1977). In compliance with this current rule, Shylock cannot obtain his contract termination and would thus be liable to fines. E.g., those like Lars Engle and Fredrick Turner claim that the game is about trends of securities, sales and promises to vary from tangible to abstract, whilst others look into the usage of links natural, mental, commerce. This theme of Venice is the market republic focused on contracts, and it has also been portrayed in recent performances. (Lewalski, 1962) Besides these stories, love is depicted as more important thing than others. Money, and grace are preferable, but love endures for everlasting. More pessimistic voices, on the other hand, are telling money rules the world, and grace alone does not govern us, rather love.

The previous studies have, however, ignored the effects on non-contractual aspects such as affection, intimacy and marriage of contractual ties within a business republic. (Fujimura, 1966) Although previous research concentrated mostly on contractual or non-contractual relationships, this paper discusses the connection between these two forms of relationships. The matter of non-contractual connection to a contractual relationship does not answer critics who view the play as a system of trade and buy or who revolve around the topic of bond problems. Even for those academics who contextualise or draw significant comparisons historically between the play even current economics, they neglect the legal, social, and political repercussions of a strategy where the public realm in the area of technology, exchange, and contracts. This article redresses this disrespect, although it is

thankful for these earlier studies which touched on the subject tangentially: the influence of contract and exchange in the field of friendship and love as well as their social and political implications. (Phialas, 1966) Political theory is more applicable for this study. As the theory shares the concept: the agreement by authority of laws; what they are, that is appropriate to compare with love (Marriage) agreement by the authority in the Merchant of Venice. Anyone who is for those who want to marry Portia, they have to pick one of three gold, silver, or lead caskets. Portia would be the correct choice to win as the Uh, award. Portia doesn't like any of these guys, either. The ones who came to court her. Back in, back in Shylock, Venice, offers to lend Antonio the money Bassanio needed. Though, the study aims to investigate the corrosive effects of non-contractual relationship like love and friendship in Merchant of The Venice.

Antonio's friendship

The Merchant of Venice opens with Antonio's speech about his sadness, with the explanation of it escaping him:

In sooth, I know not why I am so sad;
It wearies me, and you say it wearies you;
But how I caught it, found it, or came by it
What stuff 'tis made of, of which it is born,
I am to learn.

Moreover, such a want-with sadness makes of me.
That I have much ado to know myself (1-7). (Lawrence, 1978)

His associates Solanio and Salerio proposed that exchange, or the passion, is the source of his sorrow as probable, but Antonio denied these possibilities (I.I.41-45, 47). Critics who offered many interpretations of the cause of his misery, from resisting homoerotic desires of Bassanio to a Christ-like desire for divine fulfilment, have been confounded by the cause of Antonio's sorrow. (Slights, 1980) Nevertheless, I will propose another possibility: Antonio is unhappy, since, on the one side, he needs a more fulfilling friendship than one predestined to contract. In other terms, Antonio requires a relationship that is embedded, rather than usefulness or profit, in any non-contractual meaning, such as Aristotelian or Ciceronian virtues. (Newman, 1987)

Venice is finding constructive ties more complicated because of its corporate goals. In reality, he has been educated exclusively in contractual terms through his knowledge in the industry. His influential dealer takes measured chances, as his wealth distributed through three separate shipping at sea, the capacity of which is usually no more significant than his capital (I.i.177; I.iii.61-64, 156-59; III.ii.266-71). Antonio would not need to worry himself with material requirements owing to his self-discipline and his good weighting of gains from costs. What is absent is a non-contractual relationship founded on universal principles such as morality. Nevertheless, Antonio's efforts to establish a non-contractual relationship with Bassanio fails because of his inexperience in this area, because he errs the material about morals. The overcompensation of Antonio contributes not only to an inability to create a virtue-based relationship but almost takes his life. Of course, friendship may be founded on a contract of self-benefit, usefulness, and advantage, but according to Aristotle, the better sort of friendship is no contractual, centred on virtue. (Boose, 1988)

This ideal form of friendship is between good and related people who want each other friendly since they are excellent. It also requires a kind of reciprocal balance for citizens who earn from each other who desire the same thing (1158b1-2). They continue to earn goodness from and with their peers with decent citizens. For Aristotle, it is the most honourable, secure and long-lasting form of relationship, when both sides are nice (1156b10 (Leventen, 1991). Most robustly, loving a companion is to love "the other guy" and so will share in both emotion and morality in a real economy. Antonio aspires to such a relationship, and despite his company nature, due to his profession, schooling, and home, he does not know how to accomplish it.

When the young nobleman of Bassanio joins the picture, whose charitable practises have engulfed his history, not one phrase passes his mouths. Antonio, on the other side, wonders about the elusive pilgrimage of Bassanio and admits that Antonio was waiting for Bassanio because Bassanio had revealed that Antonio wanted support once again (i.e., 119-21). In the first position, Bassanio avoids the issue of Antonio and just accepts his deception but declines to protest because:

My chief care
Is to come somewhat off the outstanding debts
Wherein my time, something too prodigal
Hath left me gag'd. To you, Antonio,
I owe the most in money and love,
Moreover, from your love, I have a warranty.
To unbar then all my plots and purposes
How to get clear of all the debts I owe (I.i.127-34).

It's interesting to remember that Bassanio doesn't just respond by talking about the woman on hidden pilgrimage but sees a "lady richly left" marriage as a way of paying Antonio's debts (I.i.161). Bassanio, who seems to be Antonio's closest companion, isn't just profligate for his friend's wealth, he's partially but predominately if not mostly, he's not just profligate for his funds, but the money that Antonio received was free. This is the way by which Antonio implies that which a measured amount cannot be attributed to his devotion (I.i.153-60, 184-85). Antonio may owe money, but at least as he defined it, one cannot owe love. This is evident in the way in which Antonio gives Bassanio more than a loan, but "My person, my extremist means / like everything you need (I.i.138-39). He also offers to borrow from Bassanio three thousand ducats a pound of his flesh as leverage for Shylock, which he detests (I.iii. 152-81).

Antonio's actions are not rational, which is surprising because he is a successful trader who needs to calculate his risk correctly. What Antonio does not know is that true friendship is not focused on the total dismissal of an excessive compromise, but rather on reciprocity based on moral principles such as morality. That reciprocity must be relatively equal too, something Antonio in his confusion does not understand to trade in the value of the friendship of Bassanio a pound of his flesh. The substance reflects the real sense of friendship and, as Antonio falsely claims, does not replace it. However, Antonio still sees the world in contractual and commercial terms after his life is spared. If Portia tells all that she is Balthazar, to whom Bassanio gave his wedding ring at Antoni's insistence as a symbol of thankfulness for saving the life of her friend all are shocked (IV.i.452-54). Portia vows to Bassanio that

she will be as liberal with her matrimonial bed as he had with his marriage ring (V.i.223-29) when she gave up his wedding ring to Balthazar. Antonio speaks in support of his friend and explains what has happened as a series of commercial transactions after Bassanio pleads for forgiveness:

I once did lend my body for his wealth,
Which but for him that had your husband's ring
Had quite miscarried. I dare be bound again,
My soul upon the forfeit, that your lord
Will never more break faith advisedly (V.i.249-53).

Portia responds, in turn, in trade and contract language, in Bassanio's and Portia's current marriage undertaking that Antonio is "the shelter" of Bassanio the individual taking on the debts of another. The return of the Bassanio ring is not from Portia to Bassanio, but from Portia to Antonio, then from Bassanio. Bassanio is, in a way interested in the Portia and Bassanio marital deal. It is apparent that Antonio recognises Portia's debts, as he proclaims that his vessels have protection back when he has met them, 'Lady, you owe me life and live' (v.i.277). Shakespeare makes himself free to see how he can finally grasp the importance of non-contractual partnerships, such as friendship and marriage. It is unclear whether Antonio just applies simply to his "life and soul," his pound of flesh and ships, or metaphorically, leaving open the problem of whether universal principles such as loyalty can be contained in Venice. No matter how in The Venice merchant you view these issues, friendship is an essential good for us and something we cannot do without. However, one of the problems which the play of Shakespeare seems to ask us is on what basis friendship can and can be established.

Friendship between Bassanio and Antonio

In a trial of his relationship, Antonio positions two times his relationship with Bassanio as something more precious than Bassanio's marriage. In reality, his friendship with him remains as essential for a good life. Antonio instructs Bassanio as he knows he is going to die:

Commend me to your honourable wife,
Tell her the process of Antonio's end,
Say how I lov'd you, speak me fair in death;
Moreover, when the tale is told, bid her be the judge.
Whether Bassanio had not once a love (IV.i.273-77).

In reaction, Portia, gazing into the mask of Balthazar, observes, « Your wife will owe you no thanks for this [Shylock] / If she was to hear you offer (IV.i.288—89). Bassanio responds that he would sell all he has his house, his wife and his estate here to this devil [Shylock], to bring you. Because of its implicated reality, the comment is humorous: the relationship between Antonio and Bassanio is essential. However, it is not modifiable in order to engage in the business agreement against the union between Bassanio and Portia. However, after Antonio is rescued, both Antonio and Bassanio replicate this error. Bassanio initially refuses the wedding ring order from Balthazar; after the appeal of Antonio, he finally bestowed it on Balthazar (IV.i.452-54).

When Portia arrives back to Belmont to learn that Bassanio has awarded his Balthazar wedding ring, Bassanio is instantly chastised for lack of knowledge of the importance of it: 'Since you realised the merit of the ring, or half of its worthiness which was the ring or your own pride in holding the ring' (V.i.199–201). Instead of the bond, the ring symbolises Bassanio's virtuous partnership of affection. He is the defence of Bassanio and discusses in three ways the explanations why he gave Balthazar a ring: (1) the lawyer was a man and not a woman; (2) the lawyer preserved Antonio's life and was thus obliged by his integrity to send it to him. (Delgado de Torres, 1994)

Bassanio omits the point that Balthazar had been encouraged by Antonio a simple admittance that he respected the over-marriage of friendship and thus presented a statement of loyalty. Bassanio misunderstands honour as a form of a bond, however: the life of Antonio is worth the marriage of Bassanio. However, love and relationship are things that cannot be measured and thus shared. They cannot be contrasted. One is loved to his good, and marriage is preferable to friendship. Honour acknowledged well that Bassanio would accept, though not at the cost of his marriage to Portia, that Balthazar should be respected just as his relationship with Antonio was. So why does marriage be greater than friendship? The response from Portia to the clarification provided by Bassanio is an indication of the answer to the question:

Let not that doctor e'er come near my house.
 Since he hath got the jewel that I loved,
 And that which you did swear to keep for me,
 I will become as liberal as you,
 I'll not deny him anything I have,
 No, not my body nor my husband's bed (V.i.223–28).

Shakespeare stated that because of its procreative nature marriage is preferable to friendliness. Marriage is generally the way that children will be formed and socialised into society: friendship couldn't do this regardless of all its values and meaning. Also, the physical and reproductive activities of marriage not only bring in offspring but also put together the body and soul of both spouses. Spiritual and physical harmony, which is the most significant distinction, is symbolised in the wedding band. Bassanio is unwilling or incapable of working on this when in dispute with affection, to realise and show his contractual thought regarding connexions: affection and matrimony are commensurable commodities and can be shared under conditions. Only by owning up to the prospect of Portia's union not becoming mutual and commensurable (for example, conducting a liaison with a lawyer) is Bassanio conscious of the error of his ways, as Portia observes: "He recognises himself doubly in each of my arms" (V.i.244). Of necessity, after Portia admits that she is Balthazar, Portia insists that Bassanio be bowed to a fraternity and 'on merit' that his relationship with Antonio promises (V.i.266–70).). The marital dispute is settled.

If Bassanio broke his pledge, so Antonio and Bassanio are not part of substantive relations: Antonio is indeed alone at the end of the game as he was at the beginning, and his relationship with Bassanius is secondary to Bassanius and Portia. While his companions, like Antonio, are after complete friendship, he could not do it. Bassanio is related to universal ideals of morality, including self-interest, usefulness and advantage. In this sense, Antonio chooses money instead of as the representation of nonmonetary

ideals such as loyalty, to such a degree that he threatens self-annihilation as confirmation of these moral principles. It is uncertain, at the end of the storey, whether Antonio has been willing to recognise and respect non-contractual ties such as friendship and marriage (Salinger, 1974).

However, it is not clear if Bassanio has learnt to respect love and partnership with its excellent. It's better than Antonio. Bassanio accepts that the assurance of his marital oath will be his relationship with Antonio and thus will be his union. Otherwise, Portia is unfaithful. However, in the contractual language of Venice at the so-called non-contractual site of Belmont, this arrangement is clarified and acknowledged. There is no proof in this storey, particularly in the final act, that Bassanio understood the importance of marriage or even friendship for moral purposes or that he understands its significance but has no practical social resources. (Rabkin, 1981) Although Antonio was incorrect to give Shylock a pound of his chair, he gave up his wedding ring at the behest of Antonio to Balthazar because of his debt. Mainly because he knows the importance of marriage, but because he fears he may lose his wife and his recently acquired properties, Bassanio can and will eventually succumb to Portia's demand to sacrifice their marriage for his friendship.

Love between Portia and Bassanio

Like Antonio, Portia suffers from the exhaustion of "this vast cosmos" in Belmont when she is tied up with the will of her father who, according to the decrees, married only to the one who transfers her hat trial (I.ii.1-2, 21-35). This trial needs supporters to correct an enigma to eliminate those that for misguided motives wish to marry Portia. Indeed, the father of Portia has connected his daughter with a contract which goes beyond his demise.

The tale of Portia is also a showcase of Shakespeare's Interest in generating a female character with authority and control about intelligence. There was much more Elizabethan society, oppressive than we can picture against women, today. Rarely will aristocratic women such as Portia be learned, because it was believed that reading would corrupt the innocence of their minds. When they were married, they were it was hoped that they would be totally obedient to their spouses. Women who have trained themselves or who have behaved they were regarded as harmful or unethical according to their own wishes. As she officially hands over all her power and resources to her new husband, Bassanio (III.2.149-171), Portia seems to fit into a wife's Renaissance ideal. But shortly thereafter, it becomes clear that Portia will never be happy as a wife who is subservient. Her involvement in the court scene shows her to be smart and educated, despite her claim to be "unschooled." And she shows this knowledge to her husband in act V, Scene 1. It is possible that the audience suspects that Bassanio will not be dominant partner to their marriage (Shakespeare, 2000).

In the marital partnership between Bassanio and Portia, this spiritual degradation is most noticeable, the latter too quick to give up their marriage ring. An analysis of this union reveals how statutory Belmont encourages all protagonists to think and behave in the best way possible. (Cohen, 1988) Both Bassanio and Portia's father conflate Portia and Belmont's estate in their attempt to treat it as an exclusive possession. The portrait, which hides in one of three cups symbolising its opposition, is about to be carried away by Portia to the recipient (III.ii.115). Although, even if bound to the will of her parent, Portia can control the result of the trial by endorsing her song by choosing the right song

(III.ii.63–72) for Bassanio, whom Portia prefers in contrast to other followers. (Draper, 1935) Bassanio will represent in the Portia song, "The world's always in deceit with ornament" and continue to pick the lead snap (III.ii.74).

The contract is concluded in the form of Portia's album, which both Portia and Bassanio like. "This home, these servants and this very same thing myself / Are yours my lord!" Portia has a husband she likes. "This ring I send to you" (III.ii.170–71). The right option of the lead casket for Bassanio would, though, intensify the issue of bringing contract ties into the marital environment rather than alleviate it. When Portia is won, Bassanio automatically owes himself to his new wife, who is not to be offered a reward but rather a creditor. Portia carries out the challenge of determining its importance in reaction to the triumph of Bassanio:

I would not be trebled twenty times myself,
 Thousand times fairer, ten thousand times richer,
 That only to stand high in your account,
 I might in virtues, beauties, livings, and friends.
 Exceed account (III.ii.152–55).

In other terms, Portia is a form of investment which has an increase of its value over time and will sometime in the future be redeemed. While Portia initially trusts her household, servants and herself with Bassanio, she later modifies the contract terms, which would enable her to become both wife and wife of Bassanio (III.ii.166–67, 170–71). Portia says that after she knows that Bassanio can only take credit from a friend of mine who has a life which now hangs in the balance (III.ii.313), "And you're precious, I'll love you dearly." She said, "as thou wilt go out, forfeit, or offer up, / neglect your affection, and be of my benefit, to exclaim to thee." (III ii.172-74). This admiration to her friendship with Bassanio parallels her earlier comment. This inversion of the familiar scenario, as characteristic of the husband's wife's fidelity, reveals not only feminism but a type of feminism modelling and describing the non-contractual marital partnership in contractual terms (Pettet, 1945).

Bassanio often sees their contractual arrangement of debts and loans as he correctly describes a 'smooth scroll't the "text" is the contract that Portia, which will supply him with the requisite funds, must "confirm," sign and ratify "(III.ii.148). The only means available to Bassanio to seal this deed is not capital, as it is borrowed from Antonio, but "Only my blood [Portia] in my veins" (III.ii.176). Bassanio may only confirm the marital relations between him and Portia as collateral.

It's because of contractual mentality that occurs in both Venice and Belmont; the former one in the characters Antonio, Shylock, Bassanio and the latter, in the figures Portia and her father (Barber, 1961). Also in the storey, when Salerio contrasts Lorenzo's friendship with Jessica in the same language, this debtor-creditor viewpoint of marriage is evident earlier: "To settlements love's ties fresh, they are willed / to retain trust intact! (2.v.6–7).). Like Portia, Jessica is linked to her father, but this relationship is still religious and parental, contrary to Portia. The choice between Jessica and her dad, Shylock, is to obey or pursue the impulse to escape with Lorenzo. However, though Portia held loyal to the will of her father, Jessica refused to sever the parental and the theological connexion with her father, even though she was reluctant to sever it (III.ii.13–14).

"From the hell of our home," Jessica agrees, following her theological conversion, to enter with her lover: "Lorenzo, I will end this war if thou held the word, and I will become a Christian and thy wife of devotion" (Ii. 19-21). Both women are linked with cabinets and wealth: Portia and Jessica, who are robbed by their father with the "caskets," throw her in the path of Lorenzo (II.vi. 35).

Formerly alive, Jessica and Lorenzo have carelessly dedicated their confiscated riches to bringing in a monk the "turquoise" (III.i.118-(Bloom, 1964), a metaphor for her father's and mother's union. The callosity of Jessica against her father adds to the dehumanisation of Shylock, and it also reveals the difference in her and Portia's behaviours. Although Jessica has wasted her robbed money, Portia has held her riches deliberately to keep her husband a debtor. If the conclusion of the play did not support Portia, the marriage might have ended in calamity between Jessica and Lorenzo. The bond between Jessica and Lorenzo is, ideally, sympathetically handled by The Venetian trader. However, disturbing undertones are defining the violation of Jessica's parental and possibly theological arrangement with her father. (Siegel, 1968) Apart from the role of Launcelot, Jessica is the only one who breaks an arrangement at stake. Portia and Bassanio, on the other side, are replete, using the relationship between Antonio and Bassanio as leverage and contributing to potential success.

These characters who conceive and behave in a contractual context, except Shylock, excel while others who do not like Antonio and Jessica are not as pleasant. Since Venice and Belmont are both contractor dependent cities, governments are melancholic, without understanding why (Shell, 1979). They view the corroborating impact that contracts and commerce have on non-contractual ties, such as affection, intimacy and partnerships, though unable to function effectively. They are also contract-driven yet contractually unjust. In such a system would only be satisfied with those who can measure adequately, such as Bassanio and Portia. Contractually contradictory ideals must be re-conceived either for achievement in contractual terms or to fall short of themselves in an environment dominated by self-interest, usefulness and benefit (Girard, 1980).

CONCLUSION

The system of contract transactions is one, if not the general topic in *The Venetian Merchant*. The Bassanio 3,000 ducats borrowed from Antonio are the amount that Bassanio spends to take the helmet trial as well as the mutual cost for Shylocked loan of one pound of Antonio's flesh. The leaded scarf, selected by Bassanio, holds the Portia image, symbolising his desire to marry her. Portia recognises this privilege as a privilege of control of her property and being sensitive to her new husband's union. In the tribunal, Shylock denies that the flesh of an Antonio is not separate from that of any commodity in a pound (IV.i.89-103). In this manner, she gives all of these ducats the worth of Antonio 3 000 to save the lives of Antonio (III.ii.299-0302). In his search for retribution (I.iii.160-70; III.i.116-30) Shylock's mentality was characterised by the Duke as unchanging until Jessica's deception, but this hating was mild by rational logic. After the unfaithfulness of Jessica, Shylock became monomaniacal.

A stony adversary, an inhuman wretch,
Incapable of pity, void and empty
From any dram of mercy (IV.i.4-6).

Despite the numerous pleadings of the Duke and the famous account of grace by Balthazar, Shylock demands that the arrangement be followed. In comparison to the Duke's appeal for forgiveness, focused on selfish considerations (a possible lack of profit), the appeal of Balthazar is embedded in theological and moral ideals (IV.i.17–33; 184–205). Through tempering punishment, grace blesses both the contract beneficiary and the giver and thereby renders the two parties holy. However, fairness is appropriate for Shylock. His fulfilment of the contract is a result of Venice's moral limits as a corporate society that is founded on contract even at the detriment of the lives of the else. Balthazar grants Shylock the privilege of having not a single drop of blood otherwise as "thy property and goods / are seized by the rules of Venice and the Kingdom of Venice," for "as thou urges punishment, thou shalt have greater liberty and more protection than thou shalt have punishment" (IV.I.310-11, 315-16). Moreover, though Shylock merely asks him for the substance of the loan, Balthazar declines to acknowledge "right and his pledge" and blames and gaols him for the assassinations that he has attempted (IV.i.339; 346–63). Shylock ultimately maintains his freedom but sacrifices his riches and faith by pressuring him to become a Christian (IV.i.381-91).

Balthazar ordered Bassanio, after saving Antonio's estate, as pay for this work, in an awkward way, and thus rendered Antonio's pound of flesh to the ring of Portia (IV.i.426). Portia asked to see the ring and felt guilty of his absence later in Belmont, accusing Bassanio of having offered it to another woman and trying to sleep with the lawyer that Bassanio gave a ring (V.i.223). Suppose Portia eventually gives up and restores Bassanio's ring. In that case, she offers it to Antonio first, who then restores it to Bassanio, renewing her husband's wedding pledge of peace with Antonio with Bassanio. Therefore, the Venetian merchant demonstrates the spiritual limits of a commercial trading system and the corrosive impact it has on non-contractual partnerships such as friendship, intimacy and marriage. In Antonio, Bassanio, Portia and Jessica's judgement and behaviour on the play this is evident: he sacrifices his life stupidly out of affection; Bassanio finds the marriage of affection as appropriate; Portia perceives marriage as contractual and commercial, and the breaking of Jessica's contract contributes to misfortune.

While Shakespeare finishes the game on a happier note, he offered us a series of characters who split up fatherly relations, refuse to recognise the relationship and view marriage on marital and business terms. The inference is that considering its benefits, exchange and contract-based systems do not necessarily establish the conditions for the creation of contractual relationships. Venice, with its democratic structures and values of republicanism, enjoyed legendary status as an early Modern poet. Venice had established an innovative government structure as a popular model for a merged constitution in order to minimise the fraction's power and experienced economic stability that looked like its democratic organisation. Shakespeare must tell us not just the benefits of industrial, feudal, egalitarian economies and economic prosperity, but also the absence of public interaction and the moral principles. How the Venetians were able to achieve this feat was of concern to the English and probably to us today. The corporate and contractual pillars of Venice are shallow and purely transactional, considering its watery nature. The moral limits of the Country are inextricably connected to religious freedom, the rule of law and material prosperity, with its corrosive influence on fellowship, affection and marriage. It will seem that this is the price which must be charged in return for these products by people in every commercial or con Contractual Republic.

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